

SVM BASED PREDICTION OF DNA AND RNA BINDING PROTEINS TO DETECT GENETIC DISORDERS

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Abstract- DNA binding proteins (DBPs) and RNA binding proteins (RBPs) are essential for many biological activities. Researchers can learn more about the mechanisms underlying genetic abnormalities and potential targets for therapy by precisely identifying these proteins. Early diagnosis and intervention are dependent on the detection of genetic diseases induced by DNA and RNA binding proteins. Better patient outcomes can result from early discovery through individualized treatment programs and genetic counseling. Through this work SVM will be utilized to categorize genetic sequences as either DBPs or RBPs, offering insights that contribute to the identification of genetic disorders. SVM has the ability to handle high-dimensional, non-linear data, provide robust performance, and offer interpretability, making them a valuable tool for extracting meaningful patterns from biological sequences. Protein sequences from the Universal Protein Resource (UniProt), which includes DNA, RNA, genetic disorder-causing DNA, and genetic disorder-causing RNA sequences, make up the dataset used in this project. Feature engineering is used for protein sequences, which provides rich embeddings discusses the distinct features of DNA and RNA binding proteins. Additionally, an autoencoder is utilized to extract essential features from protein sequences related to genetic disorders, enhancing the model's ability to predict these disorders accurately. Then SVM model is trained using features extracted from autoencoder and feature engineering, and then used to predict whether protein sequences cause genetic disorders.

Keywords – DNA and RNA Binding Proteins, Genetic Disorder Prediction, SVM, ProtBERT, Autoencoder.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in computational biology have reshaped our knowledge of genetic disorders and the mechanisms underlying them. The study of DNA and RNA binding proteins, which are essential for both the development of diseases and genetic regulation, is one major area of focus. Nucleic acid-binding proteins, which include both RNA- and DNA-binding proteins, are essential for a variety of biological mechanisms. It is necessary to identify DBPs and RBPs from the primary sequences in order to investigate protein-nucleic acid interactions in more detail. Support vector machines (SVM), in particular, are a type of machine learning technique that has become a potent tool for genetic disorder prediction and biological data analysis. By using these methods, we can better understand protein sequences and enhance their capacity to identify and manage genetic disorders.

In computational biology and bioinformatics, identifying DNA and RNA binding proteins linked to genetic disorders is an essential task. Comprehending the function of these proteins can offer significant understanding into the mechanisms that underlie genetic disorders and facilitate the creation of innovative therapeutic approaches. However, because of the intricate connections between amino acids and protein functions, predicting these proteins from protein sequences is a difficult task. Many of the computational techniques currently in use have drawbacks, including low

model performance, data sparsity, and high dimensionality. In this situation, recognizing RNA and DNA binding proteins appears to be a promising use of machine learning models, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM). SVMs have been successfully used in a variety of bioinformatics tasks and are well-known for their capacity to handle high-dimensional data. This project aims to improve our ability to predict genetic disorders caused by DNA and RNA binding proteins by utilizing the power of SVMs and cutting-edge feature extraction techniques like autoencoders and feature engineering. The potential impact this work could have on computational biology and its implications for enhancing genetic disorder diagnosis and treatment methods are what drive this research.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Related works are explained in section 2. Proposed system are presented in section 3. Experiments and results are presented in section 4. Concluding remarks are given in section 5.

2. RELATED WORKS

N. Wang et al[1] proposed iDRBP-EL : Utilizing Hierarchical Ensemble Learning to Determine DNA and RNA Binding Proteins. In order to examine the effects of every level in iDRBP-EL performance via hierarchical ensemble learning, a series of ablation experiments were created and carried out utilizing 10-fold cross-validation on benchmark datasets. To further investigate molecular interactions, precise and high-throughput annotation from extensive protein sequences of potential DBPs and RBPs is essential. In this work, they created the iDRBP-EL predictor, which uses hierarchical ensemble learning to combine various data, classifiers, and features in order to accurately determine DBPs and RBPs. iDRBP-EL, an approach based on sequence is used to anticipate DNA and RNA-binding proteins from various species. The performance and generalization of iDRBP-EL are enhanced by hierarchical ensemble learning. According to a related study, DBPs' prediction accuracy within a single species can be enhanced by gene expression signatures. Since the gene expression signatures are not available for every species, it is challenging to incorporate them into iDRBP-EL.

Du X et.al[2] proposed the prediction of RNA and DNA binding proteins using deep multi-label joint learning. Understanding DNA- and RNA-binding proteins (DBPs and RBPs) is not only made easier by their recognition, but it is also a difficult task. Previous research has demonstrated that because these proteins have distinct binding domains, they are typically regarded as distinct entities. Furthermore, because DBPs and RBPs are so similar, a high cross-prediction rate can arise from the predictor of DBPs being able to forecast RBPs as DBPs and vice versa. They have proposed a revolutionary deep multi-label cooperative learning system in this work to capitalize on the connection between binding proteins and many labels. To investigate multi-scale context hidden information, a multi-label variant network is first created. The possible relationship between labels is then mined using multi-label Long Short-Term Memory (multiLSTM).

X. Gao et al[3] Presented a novel predictor, termed iRBP-Motif-PSSM, that combines the Motif-PSSM with a number of sequence-based features. It is based on the SVM-based Collaborative Learning approach. The findings suggest that iRBP-Motif-PSSM is a valuable instrument for biological study, as it demonstrated excellent comparability and even surpassed the other techniques currently in use for the recognition of RNA-binding proteins. In cells, RNAs and RNA-binding proteins can combine to create a nuclear ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex, which is involved in the control of genes and additional essential biological functions. One of the main research challenges and hot topics is how to forecast the proteins that bind RNA with accuracy. In this paper, a novel computational predictor known as iRBP-Motif-PSSM is proposed, which combines motif data with evolutionary information learned from Position Specific Scoring Matrixes to identify RNA-binding proteins. Collaborative learning was used to solve the predictor's unpredictability issue. The outcomes of the experiment demonstrated that iRBP-Motif-PSSM exceeded other techniques in the field to identify NA-binding proteins, suggesting that the method is valuable for biological analysis.

Nadav et al. [4] proposed ProteinBERT: A Universal Deep Learning Model of Protein Sequence and Function. Recently, self-supervised deep language modeling has been applied to biological sequences with remarkable success across natural language tasks. On the other hand, pretraining techniques and models currently in use are tailored and idealized for text analysis. They present ProteinBERT, a deep language model developed in particular with proteins in mind. Their pretraining technique integrates a new goal of predicting Gene Ontology (GO) annotations with language modeling. They presented new architectural components that greatly increase the model's efficiency and flexibility with extended sequences. Local and worldwide representations are part of ProteinBERT's architecture. Even while it employs a far faster and smaller model than rival deep-learning techniques, ProteinBERT achieves close to cutting-edge performance and occasionally beats it—on numerous standards include post-translational modifications, protein structure, and biophysical characteristics, among other protein features.

When evaluated to other state-of-the-art protein language models, ProteinBERT is incredibly economical in terms of size, computation, and memory. They contend that language modeling in proteins is a natural extension to include GO annotations. Additionally, ablation testing was done to examine the impact of the pretraining job for GO-annotation,

and the results showed that it helped certain benchmarks. ProteinBERT supports incredibly long sequences. The way the model uses global attention layers is fundamental to its adaptability. Because global attention is compact, it makes it easier to inspect the attention of the model.

Ma X et al[5] identified DNA Binding Protein Using Support Vector Machine with Sequence Information.

Using the SVM-SMO algorithm, a prediction model for DNA-binding proteins was developed by combining BP and NB with physicochemical property features and evolutionary information feature (EI). This allowed for the determination of the significance of those two features. The anticipated binding of DNA or RNA, identification of protein-protein interactions, recognition of protein folds, and classification of protein families were all typically aided by physicochemical property features. Each amino acid has six biological properties: solvent accessibility, secondary structure, polarity, polarizability, hydrophobicity, and normalized Van der Waals volume were combined to create this feature. The characteristics of proteins that bind and do not bind DNA can shed light on the significance of BP and NBP characteristics. It is clear that every DNA-binding protein contains multiple DNA-binding residues. Compared to nonbinding proteins, DNA-binding proteins should have a significantly higher concentration of DNA-binding residues. Additionally, there are regular patterns in the structural distribution of residues that bind DNA. DNA-binding proteins characteristics were disclosed by two BP feature components, one for the sequence level and the other for the spatial level. Unlike proteins that bind DNA, nonbinding proteins should have a substantially larger percentage of nonbinding residues. Therefore, it makes sense to suggest the NBP feature. It is possible for BP and NBP are used to differentiate between nonbinding and binding DNA proteins with success.

Zhao Z et al[6] identified DNA Binding Proteins Through Extreme Gradient Boosting Algorithm. Currently, numerous computational techniques developed to identify DBPs; of these, computational techniques based on machine learning (ML) algorithms have demonstrated exceptional performance. Compared to other methods, this one achieves satisfactory results while utilizing fewer features and more straightforward recognition techniques. First, extracted characteristics in order from the same set of DBPs using six feature extraction techniques. After that, the feature data is combined, and the data are standardized. Eventually, an efficient predictive model is built using the extreme gradient boosting model. This paper suggests a way to predict DBPs by splicing sequence feature information and applying the XGBoost algorithm. MATLAB splices multiple sequence features to create the final sequence feature. Z-Score standardization is used in the data processing process to increase data uniformity and fortify the connection between data attributes and data tags. Max Relevance Max Distance (MRMD) is used in the experiment to lower the data's dimensionality, which lowers the data's characteristics. Three stages are involved in the dimensionality reduction process by MRMD, which evaluates data independence using a distance function.

Feifei et.al[7] proposed Deep Learning model for Multiclass Classification and Identification of Binding Proteins for Nucleic Acids. The prediction of nucleic acid binding protein(NABP) faces two obstacles: the first is the issue of disregarding (DNA RNA binding proteins)DRBPs, and the subsequent one is the issue of cross-forecasting. Very little from the earlier research was discovered. With a focus on these two issues, this study developed a NABP predictor known as DeepMC-iNABP in an effort to deal with these challenges through the use of deep learning techniques and a multiclass classification strategy. In order to identify the NABPs, the traditional deep learning model, whose design integrates LSTM and CNN deep neural networks based on one-hot encoding, sequence encoding was built. The study's findings indicate that DeepMC-iNABP partially resolves the cross-prediction issue. These findings are probably connected to the multiclass classification approach used in this work, where the classification model was trained using RBPs and DBPs as various class data.

Four of the five proteins that DeepMC-iNABP identified as DRBPs are actual DRBPs. A multiclass categorizer (the second degree) and a binary categorizer (the first degree) make up the DeepDRBP-2L predictor. At last, it may now be classified as nonNABP, DBP, RBP, and DRBP thanks to the two-level strategy. Nevertheless, despite the fact that primary protein sequences can be automatically used by a deep neural network-based model to extract characteristics, sequence representation learning—which is crucial for identifying DBPs and RBPs—may be impacted by the sequences of similarity between RBPs and DBPs.

Wang et al[8] proposed EDCNN for enabling the recognition of genome-wide RNA binding proteins. An advantageous feature of deep convolution neural networks is their ability to handle sparse and high-dimensional data. To find protein-RNA interactions, an evolutionary deep convolutional neural network (EDCNN) is suggested by combining gradient descent and evolutionary optimization to improve deep conventional neural networks, thereby improving the effectiveness of deep convolution neural networks even further. Specifically, EDCNN is an algorithm that is complimentary and blends evolutionary algorithms with various gradient descent models. The global and local hyperparameters of the model are optimized using the gradient descent technique. Both local and global CNN are used to train the model. Not for the worldwide CNN model, but for the local one, RNA sequences are divided into several sequences of fixed length for this purpose. The nucleotide sequences are then subsequently converted into a two-dimensional one-hot encoding matrix after being stretched to the longest possible length allowed within the training set. Several local models are trained using one-hot matrices containing split up RNA sequences, and one one-hot matrix

containing an entire RNA sequence is used to train global CNNs. Different gradient descent techniques, such as Adam or stochastic gradient descent (SGD), are applied after RNA sequence data processing to make the global and local models more optimal separately. The ability to conduct training in parallel is one benefit of EDCNN. In order to create the next generation population and assign the individuals of the future generation to the guidance process users, the central server is used to execute the evolutionary algorithm phase. EDCNN takes the same amount of time to optimize both local and global model attributes in parallel when utilizing a single optimizer, which is acceptable.

Barukab et al[9] proposed DNAPred Prot for DNA-binding protein recognition by composition- and position-based feature analysis. DNA is regarded as the cell's outline. It included all the information required to develop and preserve the characteristic of an organism. What defines a living thing as such is its DNA. DNA functions like transcription, repair, and regulation are all regulated by protein interactions with DNA. Finding these proteins is essential to comprehending how genes are regulated. Numerous techniques, though expensive and time-consuming, have been created to recognize the DNA binding sites and proteins according to their structures and sequences. As a result, the "DNAPred Prot" methodology was developed, which efficiently and effectively predicts DNA-binding proteins using a variety of features from protein sequences that are reliant on both position and frequency. When it comes to the prediction of DNA binding proteins, DNAPred Prot outperforms other previously suggested models in terms of accuracy. The results of DNAPred Prot can also be seen graphically; additionally, characteristic curves for receiver operation for every testing method were completed for a more accurate and effective examination.

Zhang et al[10] proposed a novel predictor of genome annotation for discovering proteins with RNA and DNA binding capabilities using CNN and LSTM. Protein sequences were represented employing Position Specific Scoring Matrix (PSSM) in this investigation. In order to determine DBPs, RBPs, and DRBPs and to overcome the over-estimation issue, a two-level strategy is used. Numerous computational predictors have utilized the two-level strategy to solve numerous significant bioinformatics tasks. The minimal degree evenmore decides how the anticipated NABP binds to DNA and RNA, whereas the elevated state determines the presence of NABP in query protein or not. The bidirectional LSTM was followed by a fully-connected layer in order to retrieve the global sequence order information and hidden protein characteristics. In order to capture the small variations in protein patterns or regions across DBPs, RBPs, and DRBPs, more CNN and max pooling layers were added. This network consists of nine layers in total: an input layer, a bidirectional LSTM layer, a flatten layer, a fully-connected layer, two max pooling layers, two convolutional layers, and an output layer.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Understanding cellular processes and their implications in genetic disorders requires an identification of proteins that bind RNA and DNA. Transcription, translation, and RNA processing are just a few of the biological processes in which binding proteins for DNA and RNA are essential. Through precise protein identification, scientists can learn more about the regulation of genetic information and how changes to these processes can result in genetic disorders. Predicting the genetic disorders caused by these proteins is the next step after the identification of binding proteins for DNA and RNA. This is accomplished by using SVM model that have been trained on datasets that contain DNA and RNA binding protein sequences that are known to cause genetic disorders. Protein sequences can be used to predict genetic disorders by training SVM model to distinguish between normal and disease-causing proteins through analysis of these sequences. The potential for advancing personalized medicine and improving patient outcomes makes the prediction of genetic disorders from DNA and RNA binding proteins significant. Healthcare providers can lessen the effects of genetic disorders by identifying people at risk of developing them early on and offering targeted interventions and treatments. This method can also help create new treatment plans that are customized for each patient, resulting in more efficient and individualized medical care.

Figure 1. System Architecture Diagram

The system uses feature engineering and autoencoder for extracting features. Feature engineering is used to extract features from DNA and RNA binding proteins dataset. Autoencoder is used to extract features from dataset that contains genetic disorder causing DNA and RNA. After feature extraction the model is trained on extracted features to classify proteins into DNA binding or RNA binding. Using the training data, the SVM model is refined and optimized to achieve high protein classification accuracy. Subsequently, genetic disorders caused by binding proteins for DNA and RNA are predicted using trained SVM model.

The system primarily contains two phases, which includes:

- Classifying the proteins that bind DNA and RNA
- Genetic Disorder Prediction

3.1 CLASSIFYING THE PROTEINS THAT BIND DNA AND RNA

Finding the proteins responsible for binding RNA and DNA is an essential bioinformatics task that helps to understand different cellular functions and how they affect genetic disorders. By utilizing sophisticated methods like feature engineering, a pre-trained model specifically designed for protein sequences, scientists can extract complex characteristics from protein sequences in order to differentiate between RNA and DNA binding. Because of using feature engineering module, complex patterns and representations can be extracted from protein sequences, improving the precision and productivity of protein classification tasks.

3.1.1 DATA ACQUISITION AND DATA PREPROCESSING

Data gathering from the Uniprot database, notably the Universal Protein dataset, is the first stage of the system architecture. Those that bind DNA, those that bind RNA, those that cause genetic abnormalities caused by both types of binding proteins are the four categories of protein sequences included in this dataset. The predictive model needs these protein sequences in order to be trained and tested. The target classes for prediction are the proteins that cause genetic disorders, whereas the main classes for classification are the proteins that bind to RNA and DNA. Building a strong and complete model which can precisely determine which proteins bind to DNA and RNA and forecast genetic disorders requires gathering and organizing these various protein sequences.

3.1.2 FEATURE ENGINEERING

The process of converting unprocessed protein sequences into numerical representations that machine learning models can comprehend can be referred to as feature extraction. Feature engineering, a protein sequence-specific version of the BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), is used in this project to extract features. Feature engineering module is able to capture complex patterns and dependencies in protein sequences thanks to its transformer-based architecture. The model can effectively predict DNA and RNA binding proteins by utilizing feature engineering

to extract rich contextualized information from protein sequences.

Figure 2. Feature Engineering

The protein sequences are tokenized using feature engineering's tokenizer. These tokens enable feature engineering to process the protein sequences efficiently by representing each of their constituent parts. Then feature engineering is used to extract embeddings for every tokenized sequence. Embeddings are the numbers that represent the tokens in the protein sequence, capturing their context and semantic meaning. Rich, contextualized information about each token is provided by these embeddings, and this information is essential for comprehending the protein's overall structure and function. A complete representation of the protein sequence is then produced by concatenating the extracted embeddings. The entire protein sequence is represented in this concatenated embedding, which captures both local and global features. The embeddings are normalized to guarantee consistency and comparability across sequences. By standardizing the embeddings, normalization improves their suitability as input for machine learning models. The feature extraction procedure produces a rich, informative representation of protein sequences that can be successfully used for anticipating DNA and RNA binding proteins by extracting and normalizing embeddings using feature engineering module.

3.1.3. SVM MODEL TRAINING

Using the features gleaned from the protein sequences to train the classifier is known as training the SVM model. The input for the SVM model is the feature matrix, which is made up of label-encoded features and normalized embeddings. The SVM algorithm looks for the feature space hyperplane that most effectively separates the two classes of proteins (DNA binding and RNA binding). It achieves this by guaranteeing strong classification performance by optimizing the margin between the classes.

Before training the SVM model, the dataset is divided in an 8:2 ratio into training and testing sets, wherein 20% of the data is used for testing and 80% is used for training. This guarantees the model's training on a sufficient amount of data to learn the underlying patterns in the protein sequences while also allowing for an unbiased evaluation of its performance on unseen data. In order to reduce classification errors and enhance its capacity to generalize to new data, the SVM modifies its parameters at the training stage. The examination dataset is employed to assess how well the model functions and determine its predictive accuracy after it has been trained using the training

dataset. An effective tool for forecasting genetic disorders brought on by proteins with RNA and DNA binding properties is the trained SVM model. The model can assist researchers in identifying possible therapeutic targets and creating focused treatment plans for genetic disorders by precisely categorizing these proteins. After training, the SVM model is evaluated using the testing dataset to assess its performance.

3.2 GENETIC DISORDER PREDICTION

In bioinformatics and medical research, genetic disorder prediction is an essential step toward identifying proteins linked to genetic disorders. To precisely categorize protein sequences and forecast their possible influence on genetic disorders, this procedure entails a number of crucial steps. Creating a dataset with protein sequences and labels indicating whether or not they are linked to genetic disorders is the first step in the process. Sequences that are known to cause genetic disorders, such as binding proteins for DNA and RNA that contribute for development of disease, are typically included in this dataset. In order to prepare the raw protein sequence data for feature extraction and model training, it is transformed. This procedure entails a number of crucial actions to guarantee that the data is standardized, clean, and ready for additional examination. The raw protein sequence data from the dataset is extracted using data preprocessing.

key characteristics are extracted from the protein sequences using an autoencoder. Neural network models called autoencoders have the ability to learn how to more compactly represent data while preserving key features and patterns. The protein sequences are encoded into a lower-dimensional space, and the autoencoder extracts the features that are most important for genetic disorder prediction. Following feature extraction, these features and the labels that go with them are used to train the SVM model. One kind of supervised machine learning algorithm that is good at classifying data points into distinct groups is the support vector machine. In this instance, the SVM is trained to differentiate between protein sequences linked and unlinked to genetic disorders.

3.2.1 AUTOENCODER FOR FEATURE EXTRACTION

Using autoencoders for feature extraction is essential for obtaining meaningful representations from protein sequences in the context of genetic disorder prediction. Neural network architectures called autoencoders are made up of an encoder and a decoder. The input protein sequences are mapped by the encoder into a lower-dimensional latent space representation, and the decoder uses this representation to try and piece together the original input. The encoder learns to extract important features from the protein sequences that are helpful for subsequent tasks like genetic disorder prediction by training the autoencoder to minimize the reconstruction error. The autoencoder can learn to extract features relevant for differentiating between proteins, including those that cause genetic disorders, by training it on a large dataset of protein sequences. When working with high-dimensional data, like protein sequences, where manual feature engineering may be difficult or impractical, this unsupervised learning technique can be especially helpful. The protein sequences must first be encoded into a numerical format that the autoencoder can handle before using autoencoders regarding feature extraction. Making use of one hot encoding or embedding vectors, for example, the amino acid sequences are usually converted into numerical representations during this encoding process. After that, the autoencoder receives the encoded sequences and learns to compress the data into a latent space with fewer dimensions. The most significant characteristics of the protein sequences are captured by this latent space representation, which qualifies it for additional analysis and prediction tasks.

4. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

4.1 DATASET

A prerequisite step for any kind of AI model creation is dataset acquisition. The Uniprot protein sequences dataset, which offers an extensive collection of protein sequences with in-depth annotations, is a useful resource for this project. A popular protein database called Uniprot provides accurate and up-to-date information on protein functions, sequences, and related disorders. We may access a wide variety of protein sequences with this collection, including sequences connected to hereditary diseases and those implicated in DNA and RNA binding. This makes usable to efficiently train the models and generate precise predictions about genetic disorders caused by binding proteins for DNA and RNA because of the richness and diversity of the dataset. Furthermore, the annotations present in the dataset offer significant understanding of the biological properties and activities of the proteins, which improves the interpretability and consistency of predictions. Here, mainly four types of protein sequences are used for training the system as:

- DNA
- RNA
- Genetic Disorder Causing DNA

- Genetic Disorder Causing RNA

4.2 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The performance of the genetic disorder prediction was evaluated by utilising a range of indicators, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score.

These measures were selected primarily because they offer a thorough assessment of the model's performance. While precision, recall, and F1 score provide information on the model's capacity to properly detect positive cases and limit false positives and false negatives—all important factors in the forecast of genetic disorders—accuracy provides an overall assessment of right predictions. Four primary metrics were used to evaluate how well different machine learning models function: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. These measures provide insight into how effectively each model predicted proteins that bind DNA and RNA and recognized genetic abnormalities. The Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, SVM, KNN, and Logistic Regression models were all taken into consideration for evaluation.

Figure 4: Accuracy of different models

The models' accuracy ratings varied from 93.90% to 95.77%. With an accuracy of 95.77%, the SVM model appears to be quite useful for both predicting genetic disorders and identifying protein sequences as either RNA- or DNA-binding proteins. The SVM model had the best accuracy of all the models, making it the most dependable model for this task, even if other models like Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes had higher accuracy.

5. CONCLUSION

The proposed work uses SVM to forecast genetic abnormalities brought on by DNA and RNA binding proteins. Used an autoencoder to improve feature representation and feature engineering to extract features from protein sequences. The use of SVM as the main model demonstrated its superiority over other models, including Decision Tree, Naive Bayes, KNN, and Logistic Regression, in this particular setting.

With a high accuracy of 95.77%, the SVM model demonstrated its reliability in the classification of binding proteins for RNA and DNA. The model's precision, recall, and F1-score of 0.96 provide additional support for the model's capacity to recognize proteins that cause genetic disorders. These metrics were selected in order to determine how

successful the system in predicting genetic disorders. The success of SVM in predicting genetic illnesses can be attributed to its robustness in handling high-dimensional data and its capacity to identify the best hyperplanes for classification.

This project's future goals include investigating increasingly sophisticated machine learning models and feature extraction and classification strategies, such as deep learning models or graph-based approaches. Furthermore, adding more extensive and varied datasets could enhance the model's functionality and generalization. Ultimately, more advancements in the prediction of genetic disorders and bioinformatics may result from investigating novel ideas and techniques.

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